

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OSHATUNBERU****FIRST NAME: OLUKAYODE****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 1%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 365 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR ACA-401D

1. Which of these is false concerning guidelines for academic paper writing at EUCLID?

- Essay formats comprise an introduction, a main body, and a conclusion.
- The proper definition of the research questions is vital.
- Use single quotation marks for direct speeches or a quote within that.¹**
- Plagiarism is wrong, unethical, and a serious academic offense with grave consequences.

2. Which of these is false concerning guidelines for research writing?

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 15–23.

- Researchers should be enthused about their research topic and be willing to specialize in the subject.
- Writers should undertake internet and library searches on shortlisted topics.
- Writers should consult primary, secondary, and tertiary sources.
- Writers can use all sources once saved directly into the Zotero database.²**

3. Which of these is false concerning guidelines for research writing?

- A well-crafted introduction should engage readers and be about 10 percent of the entire document.
- Writers are to establish the gaps in prior research, state the significance of answering the research question, and highlight the research claim.
- Writers are to forward their first drafts to their supervisors for input after proper editing and revision.
- Writers are to implement all advice from supervisors and experienced readers.³**

4. Which of these is false regarding data presentation?

- Present few and large quantitative data graphically.⁴**
- Data presentation could be via graphs, tables, and charts.
- Use tables when the focus is on specific values.

² Laurent Cleenewerck, *Zotero Training 02* (Vimeo), 2016.

³ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 127.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 84.

- Use line graphs and bar charts for trend assessment or when comparing discrete items.
5. Which of these is incorrect regarding the citation of journals using the notes-bibliography style?
- Template for books is valid for journals.
- Replace publisher details with the journal's title, volume, and issue number.
- Insert the Uniform Resource Locator after the page number.⁵**
- Use Italics for large entities such as books and journals.
6. Which of the following is not a reliable way of safeguarding online sources other than published books and journals from changes or disappearing at short notice?
- Screenshots.
- Documenting the Uniform Record Locator.
- Documenting the Digital Object Identifier.
- Include information about the format.⁶**
7. Which of these might be excluded from a research dissertation title?
- Participants.
- Setting.⁷**

⁵ Ibid., 153.

⁶ Ibid., 144.

⁷ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 31–32.

- Variables.
 - Treatment.
8. The following is correct regarding the dissertation literature review, except.
- Highlight the adopted theory and methodology.
 - There is no restriction on the selection of literature based on field or publication year.
 - Research questions are to fill all gaps identified during the literature review.⁸**
 - Include unconsidered research questions discovered during a cursory literature review in the suggestions for further research.
9. Which of these is at variance with language-related instructions in the European Commission English Style Guide?
- Write correspondences within EU countries in UK English.
 - Uppercase acronyms of up to five letter cases and write those above five letters in initial letters.
 - Spellings of geographical names of places should comply with native form.
 - Untranslated foreign-language abbreviations should comply with the European Commission Style Guide capitalization conventions.⁹**

⁸ Ibid., 39.

⁹ European Commission, *European Commission Style Guide*, 8th ed. (European Commission, 2021), 45.

10. Which of these is at variance with legislation and funding-related instructions in the European Commission English Style Guide?

- Acquis could refer to primary or secondary legislation, declarations, and resolutions adopted by the EU.
- Full titles of treaties should be stated in the legislation, and subdivisions of legislation should be quoted verbatim.
- The Multinational Financial framework provides for EU expenditure over a 5-year period.¹⁰**
- EU and its institutions are funded from revenue accruing from taxes and levies on member states.

¹⁰ Ibid., 84–93.

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